

The Effects of Infill Percentages on Screw Peak Insertion Torque in 3D Printed Model for Dental Implant Placement Simulation

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Abstract

This study aims to investigate the impact of infill percentage on the screw insertion torque in 3D printed models, as well as to produce 3D printed models with insertion torque values comparable to bones of varying densities.

9 3D-printed block models were designed with varying infill percentages (20-100%) using a gyroid pattern with 2 mm. solid layer to simulate trabecular bone with cortical cortex. 180 pieces of self-tapping screws were inserted, 20 pieces per block. Insertion torque values were obtained by calibrated digital torque meter. The descriptive and analysis statistics were performed. Welch's ANOVA was used to evaluate group differences. Post hoc analysis was conducted using the Games-Howell test. A simple linear regression was performed to evaluate the correlation between infill density and peak insertion torque. Lastly, one sample T-test was used to compare experiment values with data reported from previous literature.

The means torque values ranged from 25.12 to 155.59 N·cm. Denser internal infill block exhibited higher screw torque values, indicating the positive correlation between model density and torque resistance. Among the groups, only 60% and 70% infill groups showed no significant differences when comparing to anterior maxilla bone and D1 bone value from previous literatures, respectively ($p > 0.05$).

Altering the infill in 3D printed models significantly affected peak insertion torque. Although only 60% and 70% infill group showed no significant differences, the overall torque range remained within clinically relevant values. This technique in model creation allows anatomical customization and reproducibility, supporting its use as a reliable tool for implant education and preclinical hands-on training.

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Introduction

Nowadays, Dental implant is the treatment of choice with satisfactory esthetic and function among the final treatment modalities for tooth substitution. This option offers favorable advantages such as no abutment teeth preparation, lower risk of additional endodontic treatment, no discomfort from hypersensitivity of dental bridge abutment, and more suitable access for plaque control than the fixed partial restoration. Despite its advantages, implant

therapy faces drawbacks such as greater expense, longer duration, patient anxiety, and insufficient awareness.¹⁻³ The drilling technique could lead to unwanted risk for the patient. The risk includes failure of implant devices or bone fracture from overloaded drilling⁴, damaging the surrounding tissue from an improper position and depth, and bone necrosis (osteonecrosis) from excess force or high temperature generation⁵. To avoid these risk, surgical education is essential for the reason that procedure outcomes mainly depend on surgeon expertise⁶.

Never practice first on the patient. Dissection of temporal bone is the gold standard with the most accurate anatomy of the selected regions. However, cultural barriers, ethical concerns, safety in the fixation process, and transmitted pathogens might be a drawback of this traditional method. As a solution, there is an

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attempt to create alternative surgery education. Fabrication of an affordable 3-dimensional printed model for junior otolaryngology resident training was built by 3D photo resin printing the CT-based Digital Imaging and Communication in Medicine (DICOM) file then converted into Stereolithography (STL) format. As a result, an accurate model was reasonable in overall value and safety^{7,8}. Moreover, systematic reviews of 3D printed models in temporal bone surgery⁹ and oral and craniomaxillofacial surgery¹⁰ demonstrated related literature. However, because of the large diversity of model creation software, printing technologies, and materials, the clinical application should be customized according to available devices and materials to obtain the appropriate surgical model.

Hands and fingers are highly sensitive to the sense of touch and intentional training can improve surgeon skills¹¹. Torque resistance – the opposite felt during rotational motion is a crucial tactile cue during surgical procedure especially in implantology and orthopedics context. Surgeons can perceive changes in torque after the transition between cortical and trabecular bones. Tactile sense of the surgeon can exhibit the histologic properties of the bone and are able to estimate the healing prognosis of the bone in implant placement¹². Table 1 summarized bone types based on Misch classification and Hounsfield units (HU), along with anatomical locations and corresponding torque values derived from literatures^{13–18}. The torque values vary depending on bone types, locations and drilling protocols. Adapting the drilling protocol to bone density is essential for optimizing primary stability. A systematic review showed that undersized drilling using a final osteotomy diameter smaller than the implant, significantly increased insertion torque in low density (Type IV) bone¹⁹.

On the contrary, Type I bone characterized by extremely dense cortical structures tends to have a higher risk of excessive insertion torque during implant placement. Standard drilling protocols may induce excessive torque values which increase the risk of microfracture and thermal bone damage. The recommended protocol for this bone type is by adding conical drill as a final step which helps reduce insertion torque without compromising implant stability. Moreover, the under preparation should be avoided in dense

bone to reduce the risk of early crestal bone loss^{20,21}.

3D Printing is an additive manufacturing technique for fabricating structures from 3D model data. Freedom of design, mass-customization and the ability to print complex structure with minimum waste are the main benefits of 3D printing models. In fused deposition modelling (FDM), thermoplastic filament is heated at semi-liquid state and then extruded on the platform or on top of previously printed layer. The layer thickness, width, filament orientation and air gap are the main parameters affecting the mechanical properties of printed parts. Low cost, high speed and simplicity of the process are the main benefits of FDM but weak mechanical properties, layer by layer appearance and surface quality might be the drawback of this method. Polymers mainly used in FDM are in filaments form. Polylactic acid (PLA) and acrylonitrile butadiene styrene (ABS) are the main polymers used in the 3D printing.^{22,23} In the context of drilling simulation, Polylactic acid used in material extrusion printing offers more suitable characteristics than photopolymer resin in Vat Photopolymerization. FDM samples made by PLA and ABS showed higher elongation at break and greater impact resistance than SLA models. Even though SLA parts provided superior in compression and tension resistance, the SLA samples exhibited brittle failure while FDM samples showed ductile behavior.²⁴

The effect of osteoporosis on the mechanical properties of the trabecular structure was demonstrated in the 3D printed model testing. As a result, a small decrease in Bone volume (BV)/ Total volume (TV) (8%) lead to structural strength and structural stiffness reduction of about 24% and 17% subsequently.²⁵ In the study of implant placement on different densities of polyurethane foam (SAWBONE®), deformation values increased in the low-density specimens. The denser trabecular structure resulted in stronger mechanical properties and lesser sensitivity to the applied force. Dense and loose porous structures in SAWBONE® 10 (D3) and SAWBONE® 12 (D1) polyurethane blocks exhibits the different mechanical properties depending on bone density classification.²⁶ Additionally, the structure of the internal model also affects the mechanical properties of the model. For example, the trabecular structure is ideal for a high elasticity pattern while the

honeycomb structure withstands high stress and strain before the collapse.²⁷

Voronoi lattices are structures that have open network, interconnected random cells which similar to natural bone appearance²⁸. The gyroid structure was first described by Alan Schoen in 1970. It is a type of triply periodic minimal surface (TPMS) that is mathematically defined²⁹. The gyroid structure provides interconnected porosity similar to trabecular architecture and are considered to be suitable for biomedical application³⁰. Due to the complexity of generating Voronoi mesh, this limits the technical process of making various internal infills. On the contrary, gyroid scaffolds also have mechanical behavior of supported bone ingrowth with more organized pattern, making them a suitable alternative in bone related application^{31,32}. These infill patterns exhibit biomimetic bone structures and already are supported in slicer program widely used in Thailand likes Cura and Bambu studio. These programs provide clean, user-friendly functions to control the infill percentage, layer of solid surrounding walls and supporting structure in printing process. Therefore, the substitution of Voronoi with gyroid structure is considered acceptable for the purpose of insertion torque simulation in this study.

This study investigated whether the alteration of infill percentages in 3D printed models results in significant differences in insertion torque values. The objective is to determine if varying the internal structure can simulated D1 – D4 bone in terms of torque resistance during screw placement. The application of this research is to develop anatomically accurate, repeatable training models with internal patterns that provide tactile feedback resembling real bones which will be an alternative for enhancing preclinical surgical motor skills other than cadaveric or animal bone specimens.

Materials and methods

Specimen blocks were designed and prepared using 2 software programs: FreeCAD and Bambu Studio. The specimen dimensions were determined based on the screw diameters and the required spacing between each screw and the block borders, resulting in a final size of 80*70*15 mm³. A solid block was first create using FreeCAD (FreeCAD v1.0, open-source

software), and then imported into Bambu Studio (Bambu Lab, China) for a slicing and infill generation. In Bambu Studio, gyroid infill patterns were applied with variable densities ranging from 20% to 90%, while 100% infill was used as a control group. Additionally, a 2 mm. solid top layer was added to replicate cortical bone structure, ensuring consistent mechanical behavior during torque insertion testing. Bambu Lab X1-carbon 3D printer and PLA filament (Bambu Lab, China) is used in this study. The Bambu X1-carbon, a high-resolution fused deposition model (FDM) 3D printer, was utilized for fabricating the test models. While PLA matte filament was selected as the printing material due to its dimensional stability and ease of post-processing. After designing and modifying the internal infill structure, the final model was fabricated by an external laboratory specialize in 3D printing (Zeta lab, Thailand).

A corded electric drill (Bosch GSB 10 RE, Bosch, Germany) was used in a handheld manner to create pilot holes at the marked insertion points. 0.5 mm. length brad point tip was applied to mark the center point and guide the insertion path. This technique prevented the slipping and lateral deviation of the screw during the torque measurement process, thereby improving the accuracy and repeatability of the measurement.

The torque measurement device (Digitron™ DBDT3, TONE, Japan) was calibrated by an ISO/IEC 17025-accredited laboratory (Calibration Laboratory Co., Ltd., Thailand) prior to its use in the experiment. The calibration process was conducted across 3 target torque values – 30, 180, 300 N·cm which represented the lower, middle and upper capacity of the measurement devices. For each target value, 5 repeated measurements were recorded and averaged. The resulting values were found to be within the specified tolerance limits, with deviation ranging from -0.22 to +0.96 N·cm. The reported measurement uncertainty was ± 1.10 N·cm. With a coverage factor of k = 2, the result showed confidence level of approximately 95% indicating suitable working conditions for precise torque measurement. This ensured the accuracy, consistency, and reliability of the torque data obtained in this study.

A total of 180 self-tapping screws certified ISO 9001: 2015 (Pansiam, Thailand) were inserted into 9 specimen blocks with 20 screws

per blocks. Each screw had a maximum diameter of 4 mm. and featured a surrounding 0.5 mm. thread. The screw was placed with a uniform spacing of 10 mm. between each other and from the border to minimize edge effect. During installation, the torque was measured over a depth of 10 mm. and the peak insertion torque for each screw was recorded in Newton centimeters (N·cm) for analysis.

Statistical analysis was performed using Statistical Package Software for Social Sciences (SPSS for windows, version 20; IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Descriptive statistics including means, standard deviation (SD), and 95% confidence intervals were calculated for each percentages group.

Normality was assessed using Shapiro-Wilk test. Levene's test for homogeneity of variances indicated a significant violation ($p < 0.05$), but as only one group deviated from normality, Welch's ANOVA was applied to evaluate differences in peak insertion torque among density groups. Post hoc comparisons were conducted using the Games-Howell test due to unequal variances.

To evaluate the linear relationship between infill percentages and peak insertion torque, a simple linear regression analysis was performed. Moreover, one sample t-test was used to compare peak insertion torque values from experiments to reference torque values reported in previous literature. The statistical significance level was set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

Table 2 presented the descriptive statistics of peak insertion torque values measured in Newton centimeters (N·cm) for each infill density group, ranging from 20% to 100%. Each group consists of 20 measurements (N=20). The table showed the means, standard deviation, standard error, 95% confidence intervals, maximum and minimum values of each group. The total sample size was 180. The means torque values increased with higher density, from 25.15 N·cm at 20% group to 155.59 N·cm at 100% infill groups.

One way ANOVA was conducted to examine the effect of infill percentage on peak insertion torque. The ANOVA revealed a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.001$) in peak torque among the different infill groups.

Post hoc comparisons using Games-Howell test showed that most pairwise comparisons between infill densities were significant difference ($p < 0.05$). However, there were no significant differences between 70% and 80% groups ($p = 0.216$) and between 80% and 90% groups ($p = 0.172$).

A simple linear regression was conducted to examine the relationship between lattice density and peak insertion torque. The analysis revealed a statistically significant and strong positive correlation between the 2 variables ($R = 0.974$, $p < 0.001$). The model explained 94.9% of the variance in peak torque ($R^2 = 0.949$). The regression equation was Peak Torque (N·cm) = $1.588 \times \text{Density} (\%) - 12.515$.

The scatter plot (graph 2) illustrates the mean insertion torque value across different infill density compared to the torque obtained from different bone classifications.

Discussion

The coefficient of variation (CV%) was calculated for each density groups to access the repeatability and precision of torque measurements. The CV values ranged from 3.82 to 10.55%, indicating a high level of consistency within each group. CV values below 15% reflect good in repeatability in simulation training usage. Moreover, each model specimens was designed to allow multiple screw insertion at different positions within the same structure. Despite the insertion area, torque value obtained in this study remained consistent. This indicates that the gyroid internal architecture contributes even internal structure which provides the even torque resistance throughout the model. Consequently, this altered infill method is suitable for drilling simulation model creation.

One way ANOVA was conducted to examine the effect of infill percentage on peak insertion torque. Levene's test for homogeneity of variances was significant ($p < 0.001$), indicating the assumption of variances was violated. Therefore, the Games-Howell post hoc test was used. The ANOVA revealed a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.001$) in peak torque among the different infill groups. Post hoc comparisons using Games-Howell test showed that most pairwise comparisons between infill densities were significantly significant ($p < 0.05$). However, there were no significant differences

between 70% and 80% groups ($p=0.216$) and between 80% and 90% groups ($p=0.172$). In contrast, the difference between the 70% and 90% groups was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$). This suggested that while torque resistance increased with higher infill density, the minor difference might not always perform statistically significant.

A simple linear regression revealed a statistically significant and strong positive correlation between the 2 variables ($R = 0.974$, $p < 0.001$). The model explained 94.9% of the variance in peak torque ($R^2 = 0.949$). The regression equation was Peak Torque (N·cm) = $1.588 \times \text{Density} (\%) - 12.515$. This equation suggests that for every 10% increase in density, the peak torque increases by approximately 15.88 N·cm. The result insists that increasing the internal density strongly predicts higher torque values aligning with the behavior found in bone structure.

A one-sample t-test was performed to compare the mean insertion values to published literature. Only 60% and 70% infill groups were found to exhibit no significant differences from anterior maxilla bone¹⁶ and D1 bone type¹⁵ subsequently. Although other groups demonstrated significant differences, plotting the means values shows a progressive increase and could estimate the range of torque which can be used as a guide to create the models. However, the exact match may require finer calibration. It is important to acknowledge that different studies have employed varying protocols for measuring insertion torque, which influence the reported values of each study. Factors such as implant design, drilling protocols, torque measurement devices and bone density evaluation methods can significantly differ. As a result, directly comparing torque values across publications might not show an accurate equivalence.

The scatter plot (graph 2) illustrates the mean insertion torque value across different infill density compared to the torque obtained from different bone classifications. The x-axis represents nominal categories providing visual comparisons. The range of torque value in this study covered the torque values gained from D1-D4 types of bones in both literatures. This might suggest that the 3D printed specimens can simulate the mechanical resistance of various human bone densities, supporting their use in surgical simulation and training application.

In process of creating training model, an existing edentulous cast was scanned using a 3Shape intraoral scanner (3Shape, Denmark) and the STL file was imported into Bambu studio for 3D printing (A). A completed edentulous arch could be used in case of implant placement for overdenture training. The cortical bone layer was simulated by a 2 mm. outer border then 60% of the internal infill was altered to replicate torque resistance like bone in anterior area (B, C). Different arch forms models such as ovoid, taper or square types could be adapted for optimal implant positioning training offering anatomic specific for education purposes with accurate reproduction while eliminating ethical or infectious concerns associated with human or animal bone usage. This model is in development as it currently replicates only the bone structure. Besides implant drilling practice, an accurate bone model with patient specific details could also be used in surgical training procedures such as torectomy or alveoloplasty in ridge defect case (D, E). Moreover, If the drilling friction heat reaches the glass transitions temperature of the material (60°C), the decreasing in torque associated with decreasing viscoelasticity might occurs³³. So, the coolant during procedure is preferred even in model simulation training.

Conclusions

This study demonstrated alteration in infill pattern of the 3D printing model significantly affects the peak insertion torque of the screws. Higher infill densities lead to greater in torque values. The 60% and 70% infill within 2 mm. solid cortical layer produced torque values comparable to those observed in upper anterior bone and in D1 bone, suggesting its suitability for surgical training simulation. Furthermore, this model design allows anatomical customization and consistency reproduction, making it a practical alternative to cadaveric bone specimens. This finding supports the use of 3D printed model as a reliable tool in implant education in preclinical procedure with potential in both simulation-based surgical planning and motor skill hands-on training.

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Bone type (Misch) ¹³	Hounsfield Units (HU)	Location (Typical)	Makary et al. (2011) ¹⁵ Mean Peak Torque (N·cm) (Misch / location)	Makary et al. (2019) ¹⁶ Mean insertion torque	Turkyilmaz et al (2007) ¹⁷ Max. insertion torque (N·cm) in location / HU
D1	> 1250	Anterior mandible	126.67 / 145	107.2	42.1 (Anterior mandible/ 928 ± 220)
D2	850 – 1250	Posterior mandible, Anterior maxilla	88.75 / 90.62 (posterior mandible), 81 (anterior maxilla)	74.7	38 (Posterior mandible/ 669 ± 194) 40.7 (Anterior maxilla/ 732 ± 163)
D3	350 – 850	Posterior maxilla	72.69 / 58.06	76.5	34.5 (Posterior maxilla/ 459 ± 108)
D4	< 350	Posterior maxilla	40.22 / 58.06	55.2	-

Table 1. Summary of bone density classification, Hounsfield units, anatomical location and insertion torque from literature.

Infill percentage	N	Mean ± Std. deviation (N·cm)	Std. Error	95% Confidence interval for mean		minimum	maximum
				Lower bound	Upper bound		
20	20	25.12 ± 2.57	.57	23.92	26.32	20.3	28.5
30	20	32.68 ± 2.37	.53	31.57	33.78	29.1	36.8
40	20	50.36 ± 2.80	.62	49.05	51.66	44.4	58.0
50	20	60.63 ± 3.26	.73	59.10	62.16	56.4	69.2
60	20	81.44 ± 6.87	1.54	78.23	84.66	69.4	91.7
70	20	107.10 ± 4.10	.92	105.18	109.02	100.2	115.6
80	20	112.76 ± 8.66	1.94	108.71	116.81	99.1	129.2
90	20	119.24 ± 6.06	1.36	116.40	122.07	109.7	131.5
100	20	155.59 ± 16.42	3.67	147.90	163.27	129.2	190.1
Total	180	82.767 ± 42.22	3.15	76.56	88.98	20.3	190.1

Table 2. Descriptive analysis of peak insertion torque (N·cm) for each infill density group.

Figure 1. The workflow of specimen preparation. (A) a solid 80*70*15 mm.³ model was created using FreeCAD v1.0. (B) The infill pattern was sliced in Bambu Studio (Bambu Lab, China). (C) The gyroid infill patterns were applied with densities ranging from 20% to 90%.

Figure 2. A printed specimen block with a solid 2 mm. top layer and altered internal infills.

Figure 3. (A) A corded electric drill (Bosch GSB 10 RE) with brad point drill bit, (B) The torque measurement device (Digitorqon™ DBDT3) calibrated by an ISO/IEC 17025-accredited laboratory (Calibration Laboratory Co., Ltd.).

Figure 4. (A) The torque measurement device was applied to the Phillips cross-slot head screw to obtain peak insertion torque. (B) The specimen block contained all 20 screws in an even grid layout.

Figure 5. Application of the 3D model in implant and surgical training. (A) STL file of an edentulous mandible, (B) Sagittal section of mandibular model (C) Internal infill modification (D) Maxillary arch model with torus palatinus (E) Sagittal section of maxillary model.

Graph 1. Linear regression showed the relationship between infill percentage and mean peak insertion torque. A positive correlation was observed and indicated increasing torque with higher infill density.

Means torque value (N·cm)

Graph 2. The scatter plot compares torque value from the study with reference from literatures^{13,14}.

Declaration of Interest

The authors report no conflict of interest.

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